

IAM COMPACT - Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan New

Version 3

Description

About this machine-actionable data management plan (maDMP)

The open maDMP will guide all data collection, processing, production, and storage of the Horizon Europe IAM COMPACT project (Grant Agreement No. 101056306). The maDMP in ARGOS describes all datasets that will be created, managed, and curated in the context of the project. All datasets will be stored in the project's community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/iam-compact>) and linked to the maDMP in ARGOS. In parallel, a report has been published in December 2023 with general guidelines for all project datasets, including a description of expected project data, FAIR data handling, data security, resources, and ethical aspects. This report (Deliverable 3.2 of the project) will serve as a guide for all consortium partners on how to manage datasets and how to update the maDMP in ARGOS with adequate descriptions and metadata for these datasets, and will be updated again towards the end of the project (Deliverable D3.3).

About the project

IAM COMPACT is an EU-funded research project under the Horizon Europe framework programme aimed at effectively supporting the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, as well as the design of the next round of NDCs and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. In particular, the project will use a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social sciences and operations research, and will integrate bodies of knowledge to co-create the research

process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance. It will notably explore the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation, as well as quantify factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Expanding Integrated
Assessment Modelling:
Comprehensive and
Comprehensible Science for
Sustainable, Co-Created
Climate Action
(corda_____he::101056306)

Researchers

Alaa Al Khourdajie (orcid: 0000-0003-1376-7529), Konstantinos
Koasidis (orcid:0000-0002-3656-4874), Dirk-Jan van de Ven
(orcid:0000-0001-9120-564X), Alexandros Nikas (orcid:0000-0002-
6795-3848), shivika mittal (orcid:0000-0003-4718-0064), Anastasios
Karamaneas (orcid:0000-0002-9677-9543)

Organizations

Aalborg University, Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο, Σχολή Ηλεκτρολόγων Μηχανικών και Μηχανικών Υπολογιστών, Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine, E3-MODELLING AE, Addis Ababa Institute of Technology, Technical University of Mombasa, Kyiv School of Economics, UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS RESEARCH CENTER, Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI), RAJA RATA UNIVERSITY OF SRI LANKA, Bruegel, University of Valladolid, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden, Aalto, Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy, Centro Tecnológico CARTIF, THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC, Basque Centre for Climate Change, Universite de Geneve, Geneva, Switzerland, CICERO Center for International Climate Research, Tsinghua University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [IAM COMPACT - Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan New](#)

Description:

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Organizations:

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Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad
Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο, Σχολή Ηλεκτρολόγων Μηχανικών και Μηχανικών
Υπολογιστών
Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine
E3-MODELLING AE
Addis Ababa Institute of Technology
Technical University of Mombasa
Kyiv School of Economics
UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS RESEARCH CENTER
Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI)
RAJA RATA UNIVERSITY OF SRI LANKA
Bruegel
University of Valladolid
KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden
Aalto
Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy
Centro Tecnológico CARTIF
THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC
Basque Centre for Climate Change
Universite de Geneve, Geneva, Switzerland
CICERO Center for International Climate Research
Tsinghua University

Contact: Frilingou Natasha (nfrilingou@epu.ntua.gr), Alexandrou Stratis
(salexandrou@epu.ntua.gr)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling: Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action (corda_____he::101056306)

Project: Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling: Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Van_de_Ven_et_al_2023_NCC_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying data (IAM outputs, feasibility assessment, temperature projections) for the journal article by van de Ven et al. currently in revision in Nature Climate Change, titled "A multi-model analysis of post-Glasgow climate targets and feasibility challenges".

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

4.9 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- The public

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.7767193

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

van de Ven et al_2023_postGlasgow_NCC_Dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Other

N/A

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free.

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Deliverable D3.2: Open data management plan

Reisinger_et_al_2024_Communications_Earth_Environment_dataset

This dataset contains the script for Figure 1 in the perspective paper: Reisinger, A., Cowie, A. L., Geden, O., & Al Khourdajie, A. (2024). Science-based targets miss the mark. *Communications Earth & Environment - Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01535-z>

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

13.5 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Other

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/12801799>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Reisinger_et_al_2024_Communications_Earth_Environ_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>
D3.2 Open data management plan

IAM_COMPACT_Study_2_Energy_security

This dataset contains the underlying raw data of IAM COMPACT "Study 2 - Energy security, resilience, flexibility, costs, and environmental indicators in renewable energy systems".

This study aims to respond to the research question "Evaluating energy system flexibility, energy security, energy system resilience in baseline, renewable, and cost-optimal scenarios". It focuses on exploring methods and tools for modelling and comparing future energy systems in form of scenarios and uses a set of parameters to assess flexibility, resilience, costs, prices, etc. in renewable energy scenarios. To cover all the required areas, a comprehensive literature review is carried out so as to define indicators for evaluating renewable energy systems. These indicators are also refined with feedback from policy-makers and stakeholders.

Three scenarios were created for the EU:

- Baseline 2050, based on current commitments and projections
- 1.5 Tech 2050, assuming ambitious measures to meet with the 1.5°C increase of the Paris agreement; and
- Smart Energy Europe 2050, designed with a 100% renewable energy system.

Results of the study have been documented in D4.9 – European sub-national deep dives (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13784964](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13784964))

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

148.2 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Other

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/13840850>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Study_2_Energy_security

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open data management plan

<https://zenodo.org/records/10849069>

IAM_COMPACT_Study_6_Interest_rates

This dataset contains the underlying raw data of IAM COMPACT "Study 6 - Interest rates".

Models used to assess decarbonisation pathways typically assume a uniform cost of capital; such assumption, however, does not do justice to real-world conditions and may therefore lead to inaccurate policy recommendations. The study aims to explore how non-uniform weighted average cost of capital (WACC), i.e., the discount rate a company uses to estimate its net present value, could influence global decarbonisation pathways.

The study builds on empirically calibrated WACC values by region and technology in global IAMs and expands the modelling analysis by exploring stakeholder-driven pathways of de-risking clean energy technologies and risking fossil fuels. As one of the largest uncertainties lies in the way WACC values are expected to evolve over time, the empirical estimates of baseline WACC values are combined with an expert-based approach to produce forward-looking scenarios of evolving WACCs over time. The study also attempts to incorporate a corrective justice dimension in its narratives, by assessing the impacts of risk underwriting for low-carbon investments through taxing corporate windfall profits for 2022 and distributing the revenue as subsidies towards high-risk regions.

Results of the study have been documented in D5.6 - Behaviour, social and disruptive innovation (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.12751959](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12751959))

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

13.4 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- The public

- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/13840901>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Study_6_Interest_rates

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Exiobase HYBRID extended to model innovative steelmaking routes | Global version (beta)

This repository contains all data and code to extend the hybrid-units version of EXIOBASE to account for new innovative steelmaking routes envisaged to be deployed in the EU to meet decarbonization targets for the steel industry. The new model was built by adopting the MARIO open-source framework.

The database is an improved version of the one described in the following open-access paper (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ad5bf1>)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Models

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1.8 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data
- Other

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/15586337>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Exiobase HYBRID extended to model innovative steelmaking routes | Global version (beta)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Moreno et al_2023_Long-term_SDGsEU_Dataset

This dataset contains the underlying IAM output data for the journal article by Moreno et al. currently in revision in Nature Communications Earth and Environment titled "Long-term sustainable development prospects of EU decarbonisation pathways: a multi-model study".

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Other

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi/10.5281/zenodo.10072816>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

DataCite's Metadata Schema

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://doi/10.5281/zenodo.10072816>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Moreno et al_2023_Long-term_SDGsEU_Dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

All Zenodo records include the Open Access status according to the COAR access right vocabulary (open, embargoed, restricted, closed).

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Koutsandreas_et_al_2023_ESR_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying raw modelling data for the journal article by Koutsandreas et al., 2023 published in Energy Strategy Reviews in November 2023.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

26.5 KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi/10.5281/zenodo.10362363>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

<https://doi/10.5281/zenodo.10362363>

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Koutsandreas_et_al_2023_ESR_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

<https://doi/10.5281/zenodo.10362363>

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

IAM_COMPACT_Study_1_Fit_for_55

This dataset contains the underlying raw data of IAM COMPACT "Study 1 - Fit-for-55".

This study aims to answer the research question, "how does the implementation of the updated national energy and climate plan compare to the cost-optimal EU plan?" However, due to delays in the release of the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) by EU member states and limitations in the models used to represent specific national policies, this study compares cost-optimal model scenarios to achieve the EU emissions mitigation targets with EU-wide modelling of the Fit-for-55 policy package. The first scenario includes sector-level policies outlined in the Fit-for-55 policy packages, while the second scenario imposes emissions constraints on overall GHG and CO₂ emissions without including any sectoral policies, in order to compare the cost-effective measures with sectoral policies.

Results of the study have been documented in D4.5 National regional global mitigation pathways (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13767329](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13767329))

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

15.3 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/13839879>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Study_1_Fit_for_55

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

IAM_COMPACT_Study_4_EU_Industry

This dataset contains the underlying raw data of IAM COMPACT "Study 4 - EU Industry".

The study started from stakeholders' questions around relocation of European Industries and associated impacts on costs, sustainability and labour and condensed these into two sub-studies:

1. The first one analysed the European steel industry and a potential relocation thereof to other world regions because of high energy and CO2 prices in the EU.
2. The second one addressed – in the context of potential re-shoring of critical net-zero technologies to the EU – the raw material demand for upscaling solar and wind technologies in four global regions, including the EU (section 3 of D4.7 (Holtz et al., 2023)).

The first sub-study on the EU steel industry involved the soft-linking of several models to assess the potential impact of different degrees of trade restrictions for steel. Three scenarios are analysed in each of which all countries implement their current climate policies and achieve the GHG emissions reduction targets set in their respective NDCs and in their long-term targets, but different steel-related trade constraints are assumed in the three scenarios:

- “NDC_LTT” scenario: no trade restriction

- “CBAM” scenario: steel imports to the EU are penalized based on their CO2 footprint
- “INDEPENDENCE” scenario: steel production levels in the EU may not drop below the level of 2019 (which is guaranteed by subsidies provided for steel production)

The second sub-study on raw material demand for upscaling solar and wind technologies builds on the three scenarios of the steel-related study (see above). Results from GCAM on renewables upscaling were used as an input to some modules of WILIAM which allowed to calculate the raw materials demands implied, which were then compared to current annual extraction and the known global reserves.

The GCAM model was used to develop scenarios for the steel production in different global regions considering trade and trade restrictions and all other model applications in this study built on these results. The three steel-related scenarios analysed with GCAM all build on the NDC_LTT scenario of study 1 used for the comparison of EU Fit-for-55 policy to a cost-optimal scenario (section 3 of D4.5 (Mittal et al., 2023)). Therefore, all policies included in the NDC_LTT scenario of Study 1 are implicitly included in Study 4 scenarios as well. However, these were not analysed specifically in Study 4. The policy measures explicitly addressed in Study 4 are related to steel trade. Furthermore, the CO2 price resulting from GCAM was used as an input by the WISEE EDM-I bottom-up steel model.

Results of the study have been documented in D4.7 - Sectoral and cross-sectoral analysis (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13839232](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13839232))

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1.1 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public

- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/13840887>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Study_4_EU_Industry

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage

- Archiving

- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

IAM_COMPACT_Climate_Policy_Database

This database serves as a general overview of energy and climate policies and policy targets in G20 countries, with the purpose of feeding IAMs and ESMs. The viability of applying policies may vary by model, and the type of inputs may vary from the ones displayed. Therefore, sources are included for each policy for modellers to find out the required details when necessary. In some cases, the overview displays "aspirational targets" apart from regular targets. This is because some stated targets are significantly far away from real-world advancement and the achievement of the "aspirational target" may therefore be unlikely according to tertiary sources (e.g. Climate Action Tracker). For corrections and additional policies not included, contact Dirk-Jan van de Ven: dj.vandeven@bc3research.org

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

48.8 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/12648253>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Climate_Policy_Database

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Al_Khourdajie_et_al_2024_JEGYCC_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying raw modelling data for the journal article by Al Khourdajie et al., 2024 published in Energy and Climate Change in February 2024.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

18.8 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

Implementing the Shapley-Owen decomposition method, generating and visualising the results, generating the supplementary results.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data used in this paper: SSP Database (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways) - Version 2.0

Available from: <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=10>

Citation:

Keywan Riahi, Detlef P. van Vuuren, Elmar Kriegler, Jae Edmonds, Brian C. O'Neill, Shinichiro Fujimori, Nico Bauer, Katherine Calvin, Rob Dellink, Oliver Fricko, Wolfgang Lutz, Alexander Popp, Jesus Crespo Cuaresma, Samir KC, Marian Leimbach, Leiwen Jiang, Tom Kram, Shilpa Rao, Johannes Emmerling, Kristie Ebi, Tomoko Hasegawa, Petr Havlík, Florian Humpenöder, Lara Aleluia Da Silva, Steve Smith, Elke Stehfest, Valentina Bosetti, Jiyong Eom, David Gernaat, Toshihiko Masui, Joeri Rogelj, Jessica Strefler, Laurent Drouet, Volker Krey, Gunnar Luderer, Mathijs Harmsen, Kiyoshi Takahashi, Lavinia Baumstark, Jonathan C. Doelman, Mikiko Kainuma, Zbigniew Klimont, Giacomo Marangoni, Hermann Lotze-Campen, Michael Obersteiner, Andrzej Tabeau, Massimo Tavoni. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview, Global Environmental Change, Volume 42, Pages 153-168, 2017, ISSN 0959-3780, DOI:110.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.05.009

Details on data preparation and downselection are available in folder 01_input_data_prep above. The code also produces Figure B.1 and Table B.3, Appendix B in the pap

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Other

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

Climate ambition, background scenario or the model? Attribution of the variance of energy-related indicators in global scenarios

Journal of Energy and Climate Change Education

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egycc.2024.100126>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640622>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640622>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Al_Khourdajie_et_al_2024_JEGYCC_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

All data and metadata uploaded is tracable to a registered Zenodo user.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Other

Other

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Boitier_et_al_2023_JOULE_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying raw modelling data for the journal article by Boitier et al., 2023 published in Joule in November 2023.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

15.5 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

This study carries out a model inter-comparison to assess the EU's path, from "Fit for 55" in 2030 to an intermediate milestone in 2040 and onto net zero in 2050, offering insights at sectoral and member-state levels.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is taken from a broad ensemble of models, including partial equilibrium (GCAM, EU-TIMES), CGE (GEMINI-E3, ICES-XPS), and macroeconomic (NEMESIS). Moreover, this ensemble of five whole-system models is complemented with two models representing the transport (ALADIN) and buildings and industry (FORECAST) sectors.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Economy

We exploit a diverse ensemble of seven models to explore how the EU can cover the ground from today to the –55% target in 2030, to an intermediate climate milestone in 2040, and onward to an NZE GHG economy by 2050. The use of this ensemble aims to enhance the robustness and confidence in the produced knowledge of the necessary sectoral and technoeconomic reconfigurations and burdens.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

Joule

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.11.002>

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/JGCRI/gcam-core>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10044337>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/10044337>

The OpenAIRE project, in the vanguard of the open access and open data movements in Europe was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research. CERN, an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided this capability and Zenodo was launched in May 2013.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Boitier et al_2023_JOULE_DATASET

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Other

N/A

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Deliverable D3.2: Open data management plan

Fragkos_et_al_2024_Climate_dataset

This dataset contains the underline raw data for the journal article by Fragkos et al., 2024 published in Climate in June 2024.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

12.4 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

- The public

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/11622856>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Fragkos_et_al_2024_Climate_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

IAM_COMPACT_Study_7_Behavioural_changes

This dataset contains the underlying raw data of IAM COMPACT "Study 7 - Behavioural changes".

The study addresses the impact of behavioural change on diets, buildings, and mobility (Frilingou et al., 2024). This study aims to understand the economic ramifications arising from shifts in behaviour and social innovation within the context of the energy transition as conceptualized in Task 5.5, emphasizing the relevance of behavioural change as an added social value resulting from policy implementation, rather than solely focusing on cost or effectiveness evaluation.

Initially, study 7 carries out a contextualisation of behavioural change by a literature review and an analysis of the behaviour-related policy representation in IAM COMPACT models (based on D4.1 methodology application). Next, it collects and processes stakeholders' questions and propositions on behavioural changes and classifies them according to sectors and models which can respond to them. Finally, four scenarios are created from applying different policies, yielding outputs in the fields of energy, climate and land.

Results of the study have been documented in D5.6 - Behaviour, social and disruptive innovation (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.12751959](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12751959))

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

7.7 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public

- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/13840914>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Study_7_Behavioural_changes

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open Data Management Plan

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

IAM_COMPACT_NDCs_LTTs_Database

This dataset contains Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) for 2030, and new long-term strategies (LTSS) for 2050, which were put in place in the run-up to, during, and after the COP26 conference.

NDC targets reflect the level of short-term ambition to which most countries are dedicated to through law or policy, but with risks of falling short if dedication is not high enough and/or changes occur in the political landscape.

Long-term targets (LTT) reflect the level of longer-term ambition which many countries have stated to fulfil their part in mitigating climate change, but in most cases not backed with an actual policy agenda. These will come on top of pledged NDC targets, to create another increased level of proposed ambition. These pledges will be included for each separate model region as a linear pathway from the 2030 NDC target (NDC_LTT).

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

61.4 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12635301

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/12648186>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_NDCs_LTTs_Database

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Zenodo is used which is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Free of charge

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

D3.2 Open data management plan - DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10849068](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068)

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Karamaneas_et_al_2022_RSETR_dataset

This dataset contains the LEAP and OSeMOSYS output data for the manuscript Karamaneas et al., submitted to Renewable & Sustainable Energy Transition in September 2022.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3.0 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.7090607

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Karamaneas et al_RSETR_2022_DATASET

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Other

N/A

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free.

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Deliverable D3.2: Open data management plan

IAM_COMPACT_Study_3_Geopolitics

This dataset contains the underlying raw data of IAM COMPACT "Study 3 - Geopolitics".

This study aims to respond to the research question "What are the different cost, energy security and resilience metrics and how do they compare for different scenarios?" (it groups 4 policy questions) by assessing the effectiveness of transformational responses to Climate Change through a comparative analysis of socio-economic outcomes across different resilience scenarios.

Disruptive events pose significant risks to socio-economic systems, necessitating a comprehensive framework to understand and address their potential impacts. Part of this study builds upon van Ginkel et al. proposed dimensions of transformational response and resilience to socio-economic impact, to create a novel matrix for exploring climate-related extremes and their socio-economic consequences.

The resulting scenario matrix yields four distinct narratives: Business as Usual, Unadaptive Transformation, Incremental Resilience, and Effective Transformation. These narratives represent varying combinations of transformational response and resilience to socio-economic impacts, offering a nuanced perspective on potential future pathways. The Business as Usual scenario depicts a society with low transformation and resilience, while the Unadaptive Transformation narrative illustrates the pitfalls of narrow focus in climate change mitigation efforts. Incremental Resilience represents a society that achieves high resilience through expanding existing capacities rather than transformative changes. Finally, the Effective Transformation scenario embodies the ideal resilient future, characterized by significant, well-rounded transformations and high resilience to socio-economic impacts.

This framework provides a valuable tool for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to assess the complex interplay between climate change tipping points and socio-economic systems, facilitating more informed decision-making and strategy development in the face of climate uncertainties.

Results of the study have been documented in D5.4 - Modelling out-of-ordinary extremes (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13840866](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13840866))

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

339400

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Darwin Core

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Zenodo

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Study_3_Geopolitics

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Data will remain public in Zenodo

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Natasha Frilingou (0000-0001-9359-9216)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

IAM COMPACT Deliverables:

- D3.2: Open data management plan
- D3.3: Open data management plan - Update

Gambhir_et_al_2023_Nat_Communications_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying data for the following publication: Gambhir, A., Mittal, S., Lamboll, R., Bernie, D., Gohar, L., Hawkes, A., Koberle, A.C., Rogelj, J., & Lowe, J. (2023) Adjusting climate change mitigation pathways in light of adverse new information. Nature Communications. Full details of methods used to create the dataset are provided within this publication.

The dataset was created by Imperial College London and does not contain third party inputs.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

143.6 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8119250>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/8119250>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Other

N/A

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

We will post them in Zenodo where hosting is free.

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://www.iam-compact.eu/publications/deliverables>

Deliverable D3.2: Open data management plan

IAM_COMPACT_Recovery_Packages_Database

The global recovery database was created to provide a comprehensive and reliable repository of information and data on the economic green recovery measures implemented by governments worldwide in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This entailed activities such as data collection, classification, and analysis to gather, categorise, and organise the green recovery packages and to examine their potential impacts on the low-carbon transition. The development of the database is based on a rigorous approach to identify and synthesize data from diverse, reputable sources. These sources were systematically examined, ensuring a broad and representative dataset of almost all countries globally. Specifically, the announced measures that are included in the developed database, account for 86% of global population and 94% of global GDP.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.5 What is its format?

Database_Recovery_Packages.xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

754.9 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104216>

Energy Research & Social Science

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104216>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15301829>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

IAM_COMPACT_Recovery_Packages_Database

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Mediavilla_et_al_2025_RSER_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying input data, and modelling results for the journal article "Analysis of the competition between land, energy and food using the TERRA module of WILIAM System Dynamics IAM" in Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews by Mediavilla et al (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115651>)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.5 What is its format?

Mediavilla_et_al_2025_RSER_dataset.zip

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

233.4 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Research communities

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15148054>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Mediavilla_et_al_2025_RSER_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo is being used

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Mediavilla_et_al_2025_RSER_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying input data, and modelling results for the journal article "Analysis of the competition between land, energy and food using the TERRA module of WILIAM System Dynamics IAM" in Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews by Mediavilla et al (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115651>)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.5 What is its format?

Mediavilla_et_al_2025_RSER_dataset.zip

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

233.4 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15148054>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15148054>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Mediavilla_et_al_2025_RSER_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Bataille_et_al_2025_EGYCC_dataset

This repository includes the visualisation code for Figure 1 and Figure 2 in the paper that establishes criteria for 'abated' fossil fuel and industrial process emissions. The paper proposes four key benchmark criteria:

1. CO₂ capture rates of $\geq 95\%$
2. Permanent storage of captured emissions
3. Reducing upstream and end-use fugitive methane emissions to $\leq 0.5\%$ (targeting 0.2%)
4. Counterbalancing remaining emissions using permanent carbon dioxide removal

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.5 What is its format?

Bataille_et_al_2025_EGYCC_dataset.zip

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

887.5 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880569>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Bataille_et_al_2025_EGYCC_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo is being used

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Frilingou_et_al_2025_CoC_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying input data, modelling results, and figures for the journal article on cost of capital by Frilingou et al., 2025. Version 3 features an update of the file *Data S2 - Subsidies_allocation* in the **Input data** folder from csv to xlsx format, to document the calculation of subsidy allocation more comprehensively. It also adds Figure S3 in the **Figures** folder.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.5 What is its format?

CoC_dataset.zip

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

12.5 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Economy

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14807257>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Frilingou_et_al_2025_CoC_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo is being used

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Exiobase HYBRID | Green steel version

Description

This repository contains all data and code to extend the [hybrid-units version of EXIOBASE](#) to account for new innovative steelmaking routes envisaged to be deployed in the EU to meet decarbonization targets for the steel industry. The new model was built by adopting the [MARIO](#) open-source framework.

The database is an improved version of the one described in the following open-access paper (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ad5bf1>)

What's new

- The new technologies have been characterized for all regions, assuming each inventory to be the same in all regions but differentiated by regional import patterns of each commodity.
- A slight aggregation on electricity production activities and commodities have been also performed, to nowcast electricity production mixes to 2024 based on [Ember data](#). Data from Ember have been rearranged to calculate electricity mixes by year and Exiobase regions
- The list of steel production technologies have been extended. Full list in the table below

The database implements in the EU the following new activities and commodities:

New activities**New commodities**Manufacturing of steam reformerSteam reformerManufacturing of electrolyserElectrolyserHydrogen production with steam reformingSteam reforming hydrogenHydrogen production with electrolysisElectrolysis hydrogenDRI-EAF-NGDRI-EAF-NG-CCSDRI-EAF-COALDRI-EAF-COAL-CCSDRI-EAF-H2DRI-EAF-BECCSDRI-SAF-BOF-NGDRI-SAF-BOF-H2DRI-SAF-BOF-BECCSSR-BOFSR-BOF-CCSBF-BOF-CCS-73%BF-BOF-CCS-86%BF-BOF-BECCSmaxBF-BOF-BECCSminAEL-EAFMOE

Instructions

To use the database, please install MARIO following the [instructions](#). The database can be parsed by using the following command

```
db = mario.parse_from_txt(  
  
path='PATH/TO/THE/FOLDER/WHERE/DATA/FROM/THIS/REPOSITORY/ARE/STORED',  
  
mode='coefficients',  
  
table='SUT',  
  
)
```

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.5 What is its format?

Y.txt

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1.8 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Research communities

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843374>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Exiobase HYBRID | Green steel version

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo is being used

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Ethiopia CLEWs data IAM compact

This dataset ensures accessibility, interoperability, and reusability adhering to the FAIR principles,. It was used to analyze the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) nexus in Ethiopia using the OSeMOSYS modeling tool. It supported the IAM compact deliverable D5.9 titled "Climate action in the sustainability spectrum". All the data are open source and can support future research and applications.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data_CLEW_Ethiopia_Final_v2.0_IAMcompact.xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

699.3 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To keep on record

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Education

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15684541>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15684541>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ethiopia CLEWs data IAM compact

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo id being used

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Zenodo is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

Zisarou_et_al_Recovery_packages_dataset

This dataset contains the underlying modelling results and figures for the journal article "A window of (missed) opportunity? A comprehensive stocktake and energy-system impact assessment of global COVID-19 recovery packages" by Zisarou et al.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.5 What is its format?

Zisarou_et_al_Recovery_packages_dataset.zip

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

9.0 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Decision makers

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15301829>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Zisarou_et_al_Recovery_packages_dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenodo is being used

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Zenodo is free of charge

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849068>

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